

A high-angle, wide-area photograph of Earth from space, showing the curvature of the planet and a vast expanse of land and water. The colors are muted, with greens, browns, and blues. A semi-transparent grey box is overlaid on the left side of the image.

6G for Society

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The logo for Orange, consisting of a solid orange square above the word "orange" in a white, lowercase, sans-serif font, with a small trademark symbol (TM) to the right.

orange™

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What are the expectations for 6G?

2030s operation target

2020s 5G field operation

5G Standalone Architecture

Networks cloudification

Networks disaggregation

Edge computing

Feedback

6G possible technological disruptions

- TeraHertz spectrum (100 GHz - 3 THz) *
- Radio sensing and imaging
- Zero-energy devices *
- Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces to control propagation *
- AI to optimise the performance of all network elements, including the physical layer *

* currently investigated by Orange

Some applications for 6G

- advanced industrial and robotics applications
- more immersive communication / communication of the five senses
- massive twinning

6G for sustainability

Need to build a technology enabling services that will provide value to the Society, particularly towards the green and digital transition

Need for reinforced **collaboration** between ICT and various sectors (e.g. Energy, Industry, Agriculture) to identify these **services** and related **technical capabilities**

Sustainable 6G

Need to define 6G societal requirements, to be considered with the same importance as performance requirements

More details [here](#)

Research challenges to define **indicators and tools** to evaluate them, and **technical solutions** pushing the limits of technology in these directions

Envisioned technologies to meet (some) 6G societal requirements

Digital inclusion (reducing the cost of Gbytes)

E2E environment impact taking into account usage and manufacturing, for infrastructure and devices, also of materials

Energy efficiency
Zero Watt @Zero load

EMF awareness

- Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
- TeraHertz spectrum (100 GHz - 3 THz)?
- Reconfigurable/modular HW for easy reuse/repair
- Ultra low-cost (disposable) devices
- Zero-energy devices (IoT tags), e.g. using backscattering
- Energy efficient computing platforms (from chipsets to cloud, including for AI)
- Efficient Solar panels (for ZED and infra.)

Operational necessities

- **Flexibility**
 - for upgrades, to support new needs
 - to **set trade-offs** according to operators needs
- **Ease of operation**
 - Automation, AI
 - Full system monitoring
- **Economical sustainability**
- **Trustworthiness**

Conclusion: 6G development stakes

- Orange has the high-level objective for **6G to provide value to the society, being environmentally and economically sustainable**
- We need to identify **target services bringing value to the society** to guide the technology development
- **Societal requirements** need to be defined in addition to performance requirements
- **Technical solutions** need to be designed to **meet performance AND societal requirements**
- **A dialogue with the society at large** is necessary all along the future technology development to collect needs and feedback, and ensure correct public information

Thank you

